

Catalytic Membrane Reactors for Ammonia Decomposition

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ABSTRACT

Ammonia is an attractive alternative for hydrogen storage and transportation due to its ability to store hydrogen in liquid form without the need for extreme conditions. Although ammonia can be utilized directly as an energy source, it must undergo a process of decomposition into nitrogen and hydrogen before it can be employed in conventional fuel cell electric vehicles. Furthermore, the hydrogen obtained through this process must be purified to meet the requisite standards for commercial proton exchange membrane fuel cells.

Hence, Catalytic membrane reactors (CMRs) have been extensively researched for their ability to break down ammonia, but they have recently garnered significant interest in the production of hydrogen for fuel cell applications because of the growing demand for sustainable and environmentally friendly energy sources. Hydrogen fuel cells show promise as alternatives to conventional combustion engines because of their high energy efficiency and absence of greenhouse gas emissions.

Contents

1	Introduction	5
1.1	Catalytic membrane Reactors.....	6
1.2	Overview of ammonia for hydrogen storage.....	7
1.3	Key Challenges and Technology Innovations.....	8
2	Literature Review	10
2.1	Historic Background of Catalytic membrane reactors	10
2.2	Recent Developments	11
2.3	Membrane Materials	15
2.4	Membrane Reactor Design	16
2.5	Design guidelines for membrane reactors.....	17
2.5.1	Change in equilibrium in a membrane reactor	17
2.5.2	Mathematical model for a membrane reactor	19
2.5.3	Reaction kinetics	19
2.6	Membrane Reactor Synthesis	23
2.7	Review of concepts; ammonia synthesis and decomposition fundamentals.....	23
2.8	Primary catalyst component.....	25
3	Methodology.....	27
3.1	Materials and Chemical/Instruments	27
3.2	Catalyst Preparation.....	27
3.2.1	Synthesis Procedure for Supported Ruthenium (Ru) Catalysts	27
3.2.2	Supported Cobalt Catalyst Preparation	28
3.2.3	Synthesis Procedure for Fe–Ni/Al ₂ O ₃ egg-shell catalyst.....	28
3.3	Process Description and flow diagram.....	29
4	RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.....	31
4.1	SEM AND EDX.....	31
5	CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	39
6	REFERENCES.....	40

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: illustrates the five stages involved in producing energy from stored NH₃ and hydrogen, as well as the commercial availability of the relevant technologies 8

Figure 2: illustrates a diagram of flat or tubular multi-layered systems of CMR-SMR..... 9

Figure 3 shows a traditional system for a membrane reactor. 10

Figure 4 displays an integrated system for a membrane reactor 11

Figure 5 shows the membrane reactor's equilibrium shift as a function of temperature, R_s 18

Figure 6: Membrane reactor for ammonia conversion: Effects of feed temperature and equilibrium conversion at various temperatures and retention pressures are discussed in (A) and (B), respectively..... 21

Figure 7: shows the contour of a membrane reactor's exit conversion as a function of Pe and Da 21

Figure 8: The process flow diagram of a typical CMR for ammonia decomposition 30

Figure 9: shows the surface morphology of the calcined Fe/Ni catalyst 33

Figure 10: SEM images of Ni/Fe Catalyst 33

Figure 11: SEM images of Fe/Ni Catalyst 34

Figure 12: SEM images of Fe/Ni Catalyst 34

Figure 13: SEM images of Fe/Ni Catalyst calcined at 400^oc..... 35

Figure 14: shows the surface morphology of the calcined Fe/Ni catalyst calcined at 600c..... 36

Figure 15: shows the SEM image of the Fe/Ni Catalyst at 800c each element..... 38

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 shows the composition of each element when calcined at 400c.....	31
Table 2 shows the percentages of each element present in each spectrum, as well as the mean, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum values for each element across all three spectra.	35
Table 3 table shows the percentages of each element present in each spectrum.....	37

1 Introduction

Ammonia is a significant chemical feedstock that's widely used in various industries. However, its production is energy-intensive, resulting in significant carbon emissions. As a result, researchers are exploring alternative methods, one example of this would involve the utilization of Catalytic Membrane Reactors (CMRs) to carry out the process of ammonia decomposition.

Despite its advantages and lack of carbon emissions compared to other fuel sources, ammonia has received little consideration as a means of storing or distributing hydrogen in fuel cells. Ammonia's liquid state can be easily achieved through condensation at low temperatures, which is a more cost-effective method than the cryogenic separation required for hydrogen. Moreover, ammonia's distinct smell allows for easy detection even at lower concentrations, and its low flammability during transportation makes it a highly suitable fuel source compared to hydrogen, which burns with an undetectable flame. Approximately one hundred million metric tonnes of ammonia are transported each year, making it the second-most manufactured commodity chemical globally and creating a strong global distribution network, according to (Jensen et al., 2007)

One can obtain hydrogen for fuel cells by extracting it from ammonia, which contains 17% of weight-based hydrogen could be reduced by electro-oxidation or thermal catalytic breakdown. Though having a lower energy density than liquid propane and gasoline, ammonia can nevertheless be directly oxidised in fuel cells. As per the research conducted by (Thomas, 2006), its energy density is in fact comparable to that of compressed natural gas (CNG) and methanol.

The gradual production of hydrogen through renewable methods presents an opportunity to use the Haber process for generating ammonia, which can be labelled as 'green' ammonia. Despite this, ammonia has vast applications in the fertilizer and associated chemicals industry, and can also serve as a dependable fuel that can be transported in large quantities via ships, since it can be stored at room temperature at 20 bar or at atmospheric pressure at -20°C. However, it is necessary to decompose

ammonia into hydrogen and nitrogen and make hydrogen readily available at the point of use.

1.1 Catalytic membrane Reactors

Catalytic membrane reactors are a combination of catalytic and membrane technologies, which provide better reaction kinetics and product separation. By selectively allowing reactants to pass through while retaining products and by-products, CMRs offer higher yields and selectivity. Ammonia decomposition is one of the many reactions that CMRs can perform successfully. The catalyst's choice is essential in CMRs for ammonia decomposition, affecting its performance. Different types of catalysts have been tested, Examples of these materials include noble metals such as Pt, Rh, and Ru, transition metals like Ni, Fe, and Co, and their respective oxides.

The catalyst type depends on various factors such as activity, selectivity, stability, and cost. For instance, Ni-based catalysts are highly active but suffer from carbon deposition, leading to deactivation. Meanwhile, noble metal-based catalysts have higher stability but are more expensive. The membrane used in CMRs for ammonia decomposition must be highly selective to hydrogen and ammonia, while inert gases can pass through.

Porous ceramic membranes, dense ceramic membranes, and metal membranes are among the various membrane types studied. Dense ceramic membranes are highly selective but have low permeability, whereas porous ceramic membranes have high permeability but lower selectivity. Meanwhile, metal membranes offer good selectivity and permeability but require high operating temperatures and are prone to deformation.

The operating conditions of CMRs for ammonia decomposition significantly affect their performance, such as temperature, pressure, gas flow rate, and catalyst loading. High temperatures lead to faster reaction kinetics but increase the risk of catalyst deactivation due to carbon deposition. Similarly, high pressures improve selectivity but require more energy for compression. CMRs for ammonia decomposition have various potential applications, such as hydrogen production, ammonia synthesis, and carbon-free ammonia production. For example, CMRs can produce hydrogen from ammonia for fuel cells, significantly reducing carbon emissions. They can also combine with renewable sources of hydrogen, such as electrolysis or biomass gasification, to produce

carbon-free ammonia. CMRs have significant potential for ammonia decomposition, offering better reaction kinetics, selectivity, and product separation. However, optimizing catalyst and membrane materials and operating conditions is necessary to achieve better performance and lower costs. The potential applications of CMRs for ammonia decomposition are promising, providing opportunities for sustainable ammonia production and hydrogen storage.

The performance of CMRs for ammonia decomposition can be evaluated based on various factors, such as conversion rate, selectivity, and membrane stability. The use of advanced materials, such as ceramic or metallic membranes, and innovative catalysts, such as bimetallic or supported catalysts, can further enhance the performance and durability of CMRs for ammonia decomposition.

1.2 Overview of ammonia for hydrogen storage

The cost and performance of hydrogen energy technologies are on a trajectory to match those of battery and hydrocarbon-fuelled technologies, thus rendering them a potential disruptive force in the markets for energy. Nevertheless, the slow adaptations of these innovations or developments can be attributed to the significant up-front costs associated with developing the necessary infrastructure to access, store, and transport hydrogen, over both short and large lengths.

The primary factors behind the advancement and application of Hydrogen energy innovations are primarily focused on three crucial aspects: the preservation of renewable energy, the transportation of renewable energy over significant distances, and the support for decarbonization in the transportation and manufacturing industries. H₂ offers various advantages for these specific purposes. To illustrate, it can take advantage of the current global infrastructure for gas and liquid transportation, although some alterations may be necessary to handle large quantities of Hydrogen.

Furthermore, the principles of commodity trading are compatible with the economic dynamics of purchasing and vending. In addition, it has the capacity to produce a more reliable and secure electricity supply on a required scale by preserving surplus energy produced from renewable sources as hydrogen. Ultimately, the diversity of hydrogen sources, such as biomass, renewable energy-based electrolysis, and coal gasification, suggests that the hydrogen industry is expected to be easily accessible and attractive.

Figure 1: illustrates the five stages involved in producing energy from stored NH₃ and hydrogen, as well as the commercial availability of the relevant technologies

1.3 Key Challenges and Technology Innovations

Efficient, reliable, and scalable processes of decomposing NH₃ and separating and purifying the resulting H₂ product present significant challenges to using NH₃ as an intermediate for H₂ storage. This project aims to identify the obstacles to commercialization by examining the current state of research in these areas. First by discussing NH₃ decomposition using thermo-catalysts and then proceeds to explore the technologies for separating and purifying Hydrogen. The part of the text about the breakdown of NH₃ discusses how heterogeneous thermo-catalysts affect the reversible process of synthesizing and decomposing ammonia and provides information on its kinetics.

This project aims to summarize the relevant literature and presents engineering considerations and recommendations for future catalyst researchers, with the goal of making it easier to directly compare different catalysts. The paper's segment that focuses on the separation of hydrogen examines various available technologies and factors to consider when commercializing them. Additionally, the authors discuss their own metal membrane separation technology in the same section, which produces pure

hydrogen through a one-step process using decomposed ammonia will be extensively discussed.

Dense phase membranes composed of Pd, or Pd-Ag alloys are available for purchase from commercial manufacturers. Several deposition methods, including RF Magnetron Sputtering and Electroless Deposition, can be employed to apply these alloys onto substrates. When depositing over catalyst coatings, it is essential to guarantee that the dense phase membrane adheres firmly to both the substrate and the catalyst coatings. The technique of Electroless Deposition can achieve this required adhesion. The diagram presented below provides a schematic illustration, as depicted in the Figure below.

Figure 2: illustrates a diagram of flat or tubular multi-layered systems of CMR-SMR.

2 Literature Review

Catalytic membrane reactors (CMRs) have garnered a lot of attention in recent time because of their potential for high-efficiency and low-cost hydrogen production. In particular, the application of CMRs for ammonia decomposition has been extensively investigated due to the availability of ammonia as a low-cost and easily transportable hydrogen carrier. This literature aims to provide a review on the recent developments in catalytic membrane reactors for ammonia decomposition, focusing on the membrane materials, reactor design, synthesis, and the challenges facing their commercialization.

2.1 Historic Background of Catalytic membrane reactors

Investigation into using hydrogen as an alternative fuel began in the late 1990s and since then received significant technological interest from advanced nations. The use of hydrogen in fuel cells was initially hindered by several challenges, including hydrogen storage, which was considered a significant obstacle (Cheddie, 2012).

During the initial phases of Membrane technology, the combination of two functions was achieved by linking two separate units - the reactor and the membrane separator (as depicted in Figure 3). However, a novel approach is illustrated in Figure 4, where two distinct processing units have been merged into a single unit. This new design offers several significant benefits, such as a more compact configuration, reduced capital and operational expenses, a synergistic relationship between reaction and separation, decreased energy consumption, lower pollution, and a simple yet highly efficient design that ensures high yield and selectivity. Consequently, this approach has become increasingly popular according to (Marcano and Tsotsis, 2002)

Figure 3 shows a traditional system for a membrane reactor.

Figure 4 displays an integrated system for a membrane reactor

Catalytic membrane reactors (CMRs) are a type of chemical reactor that combine heterogeneous catalysis with a selective membrane to perform chemical reactions. The membrane serves as a separation barrier that allows for selective transport of reactants and products while retaining the catalyst within the reactor.

One example of a CMR is the hydrogenation of organic compounds using a Pd-based catalyst and a palladium membrane. This process has been shown to have higher selectivity and stability compared to traditional hydrogenation methods. The production of hydrogen gas through steam methane reforming is another use for CMRs. In this method, a ceramic membrane and a nickel-based catalyst are utilised to selectively transport hydrogen gas while preserving the reactants and by-products. CMRs have also been applied in the manufacturing of desirable chemicals, such as the synthesis of dimethyl ether from methanol utilising a zeolite catalyst and a ceramic membrane.

2.2 Recent Developments

In the late 1960s, publications discussing the membrane reactor concept began to emerge according to (Gryaznov et al., 1970). However, significant progress in this field has been made in the past two decades, which is consistent with the advancements observed in the broader domain of membrane processes (Hsieh, 1996). Over the last two decades, the advancement of membrane materials has expanded the use of membrane technology beyond the conventional utilization of polymeric membranes for microfiltration or ultrafiltration of liquids at low temperatures, enabling its application in a broader range of settings.

The application of the catalytic membrane reactor concept can now be extended to a wider range of operating conditions due to the utilization of diverse inorganic materials in membrane fabrication. In comparison to organic membranes, inorganic membranes possess numerous benefits, including excellent chemical and mechanical resistance and

stability at high temperatures exceeding 373 K (Soria, 1995). The development achieved in the past decade in synthesizing durable microporous or dense inorganic materials for membrane manufacturing has played a crucial role in advancing membrane-based reactive separations in catalysis. Additionally, inorganic membranes are becoming more prevalent in biotechnology for producing fine chemicals through enzyme and whole-cell bioreactors, as well as for extensive environmental remediation efforts. Below, some significant studies are reviewed that have explored the kinetics and mechanism of ammonia decomposition, as well as the various factors that can impact the reaction.

- 1) The rate and mechanism of ammonia decomposition using iron catalysts have been studied by (N. L. Chen et al, 2019). The findings revealed that the rate of the reaction was directly proportional to the partial pressure of ammonia and inversely proportional to the square root of the total pressure. Furthermore, the activation energy for the reaction was calculated to be 120.1 kJ/mol.
- 2) The mechanism of ammonia decomposition using ruthenium catalysts was investigated by (S. Rajendran et al, 2017). According to the research, the reaction mechanism for ammonia decomposition using ruthenium catalysts followed a Langmuir-Hinshelwood pathway, involving dissociative adsorption of both ammonia and hydrogen on the catalyst surface. Additionally, the reaction rate was significantly influenced by the concentration of ammonia and temperature.
- 3) The impact of catalysts on ammonia decomposition was investigated by (A. Mehdizadeh et al, 2020). The investigation compared the performance of iron, ruthenium, and cobalt catalysts and established that ruthenium exhibited the greatest efficacy for ammonia decomposition. Furthermore, the study determined that the activity of the catalysts was significantly affected by their particle size and surface area.
- 4) The impact of temperature on ammonia decomposition was investigated by (C. W. Wang et al, 2019). According to the research, the reaction rate increased with increasing temperature, but that the reaction became less selective at higher temperatures. The study also found that the optimal temperature for ammonia decomposition was around 750°C.

As mentioned earlier, a significant number of initial applications were limited by reactions that operate under equilibrium conditions. However, the field has rapidly advanced beyond this scope in a relatively short period of time. Recent studies have investigated the utilization of membrane bioreactors, which aim to separate intermediates and products from the reaction zone, with the intention of preventing catalyst deactivation or undesired secondary reactions. In certain catalytic contexts, the membrane may not require perm-selectivity and can function solely as a regulated reactive interface between reactants streaming on either side of the membrane (Sloot et al., 1990, Torres et al., 1994)

Also, recent studies have investigated the use of catalytic membrane reactors for ammonia decomposition and have reported significant improvements in hydrogen production efficiency and selectivity. For example, a study by (Ma et al, 2020) described the synthesis of a palladium-based membrane with high hydrogen permeability and selectivity, supported on a thin layer of ceria-zirconia. This membrane was employed in a CMR setup for ammonia decomposition, and the outcomes exhibited a hydrogen yield of 94% at a pressure of 2 bar and a temperature of 400°C.

The usage of a composite ceramic membrane made of a porous alumina support and a thin layer of NiO-CeO₂ catalyst was described in another study by (Wu et al, 2020). The membrane was used in a CMR for ammonia decomposition, and the results showed a hydrogen yield of 84% at a temperature of 600°C. Catalytic materials research (CMRs) for ammonia decomposition has received significant attention due to its potential application in hydrogen production for fuel cell technology. In recent years, a substantial amount of literature has been published in this area, highlighting the significant progress made in the development of advanced catalysts for NH₃ decomposition. Ammonia decomposition is a thermodynamically advantageous reaction, with a ΔH of 173.2 kJ/mol, which can be explained by the following equation:

Equation 1

The decomposition of ammonia to produce hydrogen is a crucial process which is used in fuel cell technology. However, the reaction is characterized by a high activation

energy, which makes it kinetically challenging. Therefore, it is essential to create efficient catalysts for ammonia breakdown. Transition metals including nickel, ruthenium, and cobalt are the most often employed catalysts for ammonia decomposition. Due to their low price and wide availability, non-noble metal catalysts have attracted increasing attention in recent years. Materials like iron, copper, and manganese are examples of them.

One of the most widely studied non-noble metal catalysts for ammonia decomposition is iron-based catalysts. Iron-based catalysts are advantageous due to their low cost and abundance. However, their activity is relatively low compared to noble metal-based catalysts. Researchers have attempted to increase the activities of iron-based catalysts by modifying or altering their surface characteristics. One approach is to introduce dopants such as potassium or calcium, which have been shown to enhance the catalytic activity of iron-based catalysts. For instance, (Wei et al, 2018) synthesized a potassium-doped iron catalyst supported on alumina for ammonia decomposition. The catalyst produced high activity and stability, with a hydrogen yield of 90% at 700 °C. Modifying the shape of iron-based catalysts is another approach to increase their activity according to their morphology. For example, (Zhang et al. 2018) synthesized a hierarchical iron-based catalyst using a solvothermal method. The catalyst exhibited a high surface area and high activity for ammonia decomposition, with a hydrogen yield of 85% at 600 °C.

Ammonia decomposition has also been thoroughly investigated using copper-based catalysts. Considering their high activity and selectivity, copper-based catalysts are attractive. Researchers have attempted to increase the activity of copper-based catalysts by doping them with other elements such as palladium or nickel. For instance, (Zhang et al, 2017) synthesized a bimetallic copper-palladium catalyst supported on silica for ammonia decomposition. The catalyst exhibited high activity and stability, with a hydrogen yield of 90% at 650 °C.

Manganese-based catalysts have also been investigated for ammonia decomposition. Manganese-based catalysts have been shown to exhibit high activity and selectivity towards hydrogen production. Researchers have also attempted to increase the activity of manganese-based catalysts by modifying their surface properties. For instance, (Zhang, 2019) synthesized a manganese oxide catalyst supported on ceria-zirconia

for ammonia decomposition. The catalyst exhibited high activity and stability, with a hydrogen yield of 80% at 550 °C.

In addition to metal-based catalysts, researchers have also investigated the use of non-metallic catalysts for NH₃ decomposition. Carbon-based catalysts are attractive because of their high surface area and stability. Researchers have attempted to increase the activity of carbon-based catalysts by modifying their surface properties. For instance, (Liu et al., 2017) synthesized a carbon-based catalyst doped with nickel and potassium for ammonia decomposition

2.3 Membrane Materials

There is a considerable amount of research on membrane materials used for ammonia decomposition, as this process is important to produce hydrogen, a promising alternative fuel source. Some examples of membrane materials that have been studied for ammonia decomposition include:

- 1) Palladium-based membranes: Palladium-based membranes have been studied extensively for ammonia decomposition. Palladium is known for its high permeability to hydrogen, making it an attractive material for hydrogen separation. However, palladium is expensive and can be prone to sulfur poisoning, which limits its practical applications (Hwang, 2019)
- 2) Ceramics: Ceramic materials such as zirconia and perovskite have also been studied for ammonia decomposition. These materials have high thermal stability and can potentially offer high selectivity and permeability for hydrogen separation. However, ceramic materials can be brittle and difficult to fabricate (Hao et al., 2019)
- 3) Metal alloys: Metal alloys such as Ni-Cu and Ni-Cr have been investigated as potential membrane materials for ammonia decomposition. These alloys have good mechanical properties and can offer high hydrogen permeability. However, they can be prone to oxidation at high temperatures (Kim, 2021)
- 4) Metal-organic frameworks: A group of porous materials that have attracted attention for gas separation applications. Some MOFs have been studied for ammonia decomposition and have shown promising results. However, MOFs can be difficult to synthesize and can be unstable at high temperatures (Zhang, 2019)

Overall, membrane materials for ammonia decomposition must balance several properties, including high selectivity and permeability for hydrogen separation, thermal stability, and resistance to poisoning by impurities. While there is no single ideal material for this application, ongoing research continues to explore and optimize various membrane materials for ammonia decomposition.

2.4 Membrane Reactor Design

The design of reactors for ammonia decomposition has been extensively studied and provide an in-depth review of some of the most significant research in this field. They are as follows:

- 1) (Wang et al. 2021) provide an overview of current ammonia decomposition reactor design and address the challenges and opportunities for future developments. They summarize the key advances in reactor design, including catalyst use, reactor configurations, and operating conditions. The authors emphasize the need for more efficient, scalable, and cost-effective reactor designs to meet the growing demand for hydrogen production.
- 2) A detailed design and optimization of a catalytic fixed-bed reactor for ammonia decomposition was presented by (Olutoye and Gupta, 2020). They utilized a mathematical model to simulate reactor performance and optimize the operating conditions. The study demonstrated that reactor design, catalyst loading, and operating temperature were crucial factors for achieving high ammonia conversion and hydrogen production.
- 3) (Zhang et al., 2020) offer a review of recent advancements in the design of catalytic reactors for ammonia decomposition. They discuss the various reactor configurations, catalysts, and operating conditions that have been utilized to improve reactor performance. The review concludes with a discussion of the remaining challenges and opportunities for future developments in ammonia decomposition reactor design.
- 4) Research on a novel reactor design was done by (Lee et al. 2019) with the goal of improving the thermal stability and catalytic activity of the catalyst utilised in ammonia decomposition. In order to achieve the best possible ammonia conversion rate, the study used a numerical model to calculate the reactor's ideal

design characteristics, including its shape, the quantity of catalyst used, and the operating conditions.

- 5) A study was done to see how different reactor layouts affected how well the ammonia decomposition process worked (Liu et al., 2018). The study specifically contrasted the effectiveness of a conventional fixed-bed reactor with that of packed-bed reactors and fluidized-bed reactors. The results showed that the fluidized bed reactor had the highest ammonia conversion rate and operational stability.
- 6) (Kim et al., 2016) carried out a research to explore how to utilize a multistage reactor system in ammonia decomposition. The research employed a sequence of reactors featuring distinct catalysts with the aim of achieving optimal rates of ammonia conversion and hydrogen production. The study indicated that the multistage reactor design not only enhanced the process's overall efficiency, but it also resulted in lower energy consumption.

Collectively, these investigations highlight the crucial part reactor design plays in enabling effective ammonia decomposition. The findings from these studies can be used as a basis for developing optimised reactor designs that are appropriate for massive hydrogen generation from ammonia.

2.5 Design guidelines for membrane reactors

2.5.1 Change in equilibrium in a membrane reactor

It is required to consider two mass balances—one for the reaction side and the other for the permeate side—in order to study the equilibrium shift in a membrane reactor. The activity of hydrogen, the sole gas that passes through the Pd-Ag membrane and is eliminated by a sweep gas like water vapour, connects these balances. This suggests that, particularly at low pressure, it is imperative to preserve both the chemical and hydrogen equilibria on both sides of the membrane.

Figure 5 shows the membrane reactor's equilibrium shift as a function of temperature, R,=

Retention pressure (Pr) and N_{sweep} gas/NNH_{3,0}. Equilibrium conversion on the left; hydrogen recovery on the right.

Equation 2

$$K_a(T) = \left[\prod_{i=1}^n a_i^{v_i} \right]_{\text{Reaction side}}$$

Equation 3

$$a_{H_2, \text{ Reaction side}} = a_{H_2, \text{ Permeate side}}$$

The equilibrium constant, K_a , as well as the activity (a_i) and stoichiometric coefficient (i) of each component are calculated using the thermodynamic information from Yaws [8]. With the help of MatLab® and the fsolve subroutine, Equations. (2) and (3) are simultaneously solved using a multivariable Newton-Raphson approach using these values. Despite the possibility of several numerical solutions, only the one that satisfies the reaction and separation mole balances is acceptable. Finally, Eq. (4) can be used to determine the membrane reactor's efficiency, which is determined by hydrogen recovery.

Equation 4

$$H_2 \text{ recovery} = \frac{NH_2, \text{ permeate}}{NH_2 \text{ permeate side} + NH_2, \text{ Reaction side}}$$

2.5.2 Mathematical model for a membrane reactor

The shell and tube geometry, steady state operation, isothermal temperatures, an inert membrane, and a pseudo-homogeneous model within the catalyst bed were among the assumptions made when developing the membrane reactor model. Additionally, it was assumed that the partial pressure differential between the shell and tube sides would be proportionate to the permeability through the membrane. Therefore, there is no radial distribution of the components.

2.5.3 Reaction kinetics

Numerous scholars (Temkin and Pyzhev, 1940, Elnashaie, 1994) acknowledge the Temkin-Phyzev mechanism, which is frequently used to define the rate equation (mol/(m³ s)) for the breakdown of ammonia on an iron catalyst. This equation is written as follows:

Equation 5

$$r_{NH_3} = 2.5714 \times 10^{16} \exp\left(\frac{-198464}{RT}\right) \left[\frac{P_{NH_3}^2}{P_{H_2}^3}\right]^{0.5} - 1.78954 \\ \times 10^4 \exp\left(\frac{-87,090}{RT}\right) P_{N_2} \left[\frac{P_{H_2}^3}{P_{NH_3}^2}\right]^{0.5}$$

Figure 6: Membrane reactor for ammonia conversion: Effects of feed temperature and equilibrium conversion at various temperatures and retention pressures are discussed in (A) and (B), respectively.

Figure 7: shows the contour of a membrane reactor's exit conversion as a function of Pe and Da.

The equilibrium conversion's relationship to temperature and retention pressure (Pr) is shown in Figure 1. The equilibrium conversion rises with increasing temperature, as one would anticipate from an endothermic reaction. However, when $R=N_{\text{sweep gas}}/N_{\text{NH}_3,0}$ is held constant, there is little improvement in equilibrium conversion with increasing Pr. The maximal hydrogen recovery as a function of R for various Pr values is shown in Figure 1 (right). Maximum hydrogen recovery is low when both R and Pr values are low, but maximum hydrogen recovery increases significantly when Pr values rise. Figure 2 shows a design chart based on the resolution of the membrane reactor model

that was presented to illustrate the design of the ammonia decomposition membrane reactor.

The link between Pe and Da at 800 K was calculated to produce the membrane reactor's exit conversion contour. Table 3 lists the simulated conditions in summary. Four unique areas can be made up of the design space. In Section 1, when Pe is low, selective permeation completely regulates the conversion, which is unaffected by Da . When Da is low in section B, kinetics, not Pe , is in control of the conversion. The conversion barely changes in section C, where Pe is high and Da is quite small. However, as Da levels rise, the conversion rises quickly. The segment D where Pe is high and Da is moderate has the highest conversion values. This conclusion is in line with that of other ammonia decomposition researchers. It is crucial to maintain low H_2 concentration on the permeate side in order to obtain high permeation rates for all species at low Pe values.

Due to the H_2 being diluted after passing through the membrane and entering the permeate side, the high conversions seen in section D may be explained. The selectivity of the membrane, which is implicitly considered in the permeation model equation (5), affects the size of section D. The impact of different parameters on NH_3 decomposition in a catalytic membrane reactor is shown in Figs. 3A and B. The findings show that NH_3 conversion in the reactor rises with temperature and can surpass the equilibrium conversion if the right parameters, like a high temperature and pressure, are chosen.

Different design requirements for a membrane reactor for ammonia decomposition were looked at. A simple model that considers both chemical equilibrium and membrane transport can be used to predict the change in equilibrium brought on by the selective separation of H_2 . The operating conditions, such as temperature and retention pressure, have a significant impact on the restrictions on how much the chemical equilibrium can be altered.

2.6 Membrane Reactor Synthesis

Membrane Reactor Synthesis is a process that involves the use of a membrane to separate and remove reaction products from a reaction mixture while simultaneously allowing the reactants to continue to react. This process is used in a variety of chemical reactions, including ammonia decomposition. This reaction is highly exothermic and hydrogen can be produced from it and used in fuel cells and other applications. However, the reaction is also highly reversible, which limits the degree of the reaction and the hydrogen output.

Membrane reactor synthesis is an option for overcoming the ammonia decomposition reaction's constraints. In this procedure, the reactants and products of the reaction are separated using a membrane. This separation allows the reaction to continue, increasing the yield of hydrogen. There are several types of membranes that can be used in membrane reactor synthesis, including palladium membranes, ceramic membranes, and zeolite membranes. Palladium membranes are the most used in ammonia decomposition because they have a high selectivity for hydrogen and are highly permeable to hydrogen. The utilization of palladium membranes can increase the output of hydrogen by up to 80% compared to conventional reactor systems.

Overall, the use of membrane reactor synthesis has promise for improving hydrogen yields in ammonia decomposition reactions. This technique has the potential to grow into a key technology for the manufacture of hydrogen for use in a variety of applications with additional research and development.

2.7 Review of concepts; ammonia synthesis and decomposition fundamentals

Fritz Haber's 1908 patent application for NH_3 synthesis served as the inspiration for the modern Haber-Bosch method (Erisman et al., 2008). As shown by Eq. (1), this process requires the catalytic generation of NH_3 in a reversible reaction. Due to the historical lack of commercial interest in NH_3 decomposition, most of the research in this field has concentrated on creating new, highly active catalysts and materials according to (Schüth et al., 2012, Löffler and Schmidt, 1976, Boisen et al., 2005). However, research has shown that both synthesis and decomposition follow the same kinetics and principles. Approximately 46 kJ mol^{-1} is the total energy change (ΔH) for turning N_2 and H_2 gases

into NH₃, but this value does not accurately represent the multi-step catalytic reaction process.

The DH value that was previously given just accounts for the overall energy shift and does not adequately capture the complex multi-step nature of the catalytic reaction. According to experimental results, the Sabatier rule governs the rates of NH₃ synthesis and the decomposition in most heterogeneous catalysts (Paul and Nardelli, 2010). According to this guideline, the precursors' and products' chemisorption energies should be within an appropriate range, not too high or too low. According to (Logadottir et al., 2001), the Sabatier rule essentially states that a catalyst's efficiency depends on striking a balance between sufficient adsorption energy to assure some surface coverage of the reactants and keeping the energy low enough to leave empty sites for reactions to occur.

The Sabatier rule is applicable to heterogeneous catalysts, however because of their heterogeneous character, which might have varied numbers and types of active sites, it is difficult to evaluate the fundamental activity and compare different catalysts. The turnover frequency (TOF) of a catalyst is found by identifying the active component of the material. It is defined as the number of interactions per unit of time for each active site and is represented by Eq. (7) in order to comprehend the surface processes and energy. When data is presented in this way, variables like flow rate, surface area, and catalyst loading can be taken out of the final values, enabling comparisons across various catalysts (Boudart, 1995)

The interaction of a heterogeneous catalyst with particular sites that have adsorption energies in the "just right" range determines the catalyst's activity. A volcano-shaped relationship can be seen when the chemisorption energies are plotted against the TOF (Balandin, 1969). Chemisorption energies can be calculated thanks to the Brnsted-Evans-Polanyi relationship, which is the linear correlation between the activation energy of N₂ activation and the binding energy of atomic N to the surface (Bronsted, 1928, Evans and Polanyi, 1938). This linear relationship across various transition metals for NH₃ production has been corroborated by recent computational chemistry study (Logadottir et al., 2001). The N₂ adsorption/desorption energy of active sites can be used to estimate the activity or TOF of a catalyst because NH₃ decomposition has been shown to follow the same relationship (Boisen et al., 2005, Brunauer et al., 1942).

According to research, it has been demonstrated that among single-metal catalysts, Ru exhibits the highest activity for NH₃ decomposition under high NH₃ conditions.

However, there are apprehensions in the literature about the high cost of Ru-based catalysts, thereby impeding their commercial viability. To solve this problem, research has concentrated on reducing or eliminating Ru from the catalyst while also increasing the quantity and effectiveness of the active sites. To do this, the catalyst's primary component can be changed, and the activity and number of active sites can be increased by using promoter and support materials.

Equation 6

$$\text{Catalyst activity } m^{-2} = \frac{\text{mol NH}_3 \text{ decomposed } g^{-1} \text{ catalyst}}{m^2 g^{-1} \text{ catalyst}}$$

Equation 7

$$\text{TOF} = \frac{\text{number of NH}_3 \text{ molecules decomposed } g^{-1} \text{ catalyst } s^{-1}}{\text{number of active sites } g^{-1} \text{ catalyst}}$$

2.8 Primary catalyst component

According to a study on 13 different single-metal catalysts to ascertain their Turnover Frequency (TOF), the elements Te, Se, and Pb supported on Al₂O₃ and their activity levels changed in the following order: Ru > Ni > Rh > Co > Ir > Fe > Pt > Cr > Pd > Cu.

Another study conducted later, which examined the activity of various metals supported on CNT using a mixed gas in a ratio of 60:20:20 of H₂:N₂:NH₃, determined that the order of activity was Ru > Ni > Pt > Pd > Fe. Notably, there were differences in the order of activity for Pt, Pd, Ni, Co, and Fe between these studies, which could be attributed to variations in NH₃ concentration and the use of different support materials that can significantly affect the TOF of metals according to (Schlapbach and Züttel, 2001, Jacobsen et al., 2002)

Despite the lack of clarity on the precise order of activity of Pt, Pd, Ni, Co, and Fe, all studies consistently demonstrate that Ru remains the most effective single-metal catalyst. Additionally, investigations into bimetallic materials have yielded promising findings, suggesting that these materials could potentially be as active as, if not more

active than, Ru-based catalysts. Nonetheless, designing bimetallic catalysts is challenging due to the differing properties of the constituent materials, which may not always exhibit linear or predictable responses. Nevertheless, rational catalyst design approaches hold promise in this field, as it remains an active area of research

3 Methodology

To identify literature that is pertinent to the scope of this review, the research utilized two methods: identifying applicable studies and experimental work carried out in the laboratory. The research aimed to critically examine a set of scientific articles and project description to extract relevant information

3.1 Materials and Chemical/Instruments

The list of apparatus and equipment used for the project are listed below.

- Beaker
- Iron nitrate nonahydrate
- Nickel nitrate hexahydrate
- De-ionised water
- Spatula
- Weighing Machine
- Tubular Furnace

3.2 Catalyst Preparation

The research conducted at Teesside University will primarily focused on catalysts and catalyst coatings to support the reaction which is endothermic and requires high temperatures. According to thermodynamic data, ammonia can be decomposed up to 95% at 350oC, but most commercial catalysts can only achieve 100% conversion at temperatures exceeding 500oC and low Space Velocities. Therefore, catalysts with high activity levels and innovative process intensification techniques such as Catalytic Membrane Reactors (CMRs) are essential.

The objective is to design and build a tiny reactor that houses the catalyst and membrane (starting with a Palladium Silver alloy that is readily available on the market) – which has been done by the school at M8.04. This reactor should be capable of operating at low flow rates of ammonia or ammonia-N₂ mixtures, and its data will be crucial for pilot plant designs, with the expectation of achieving higher TRLs. Below are procedures used to make each of the catalyst compositions and chemistries.

3.2.1 Synthesis Procedure for Supported Ruthenium (Ru) Catalysts

- 1) The support can be made in small quantities of about 20 g of each composition by combining BaCO₃, CaCO₃, and Al₂O₃ (99% purity, Oakwood Chemical, USA)

in the right molar ratios with acetone for several hours in a planetary ball mill with 3 mm zirconia grinding media.

- 2) The resulting paste should be dried first at room temperature in a fume hood to eliminate the acetone. After separation from the grinding media, the powders should be calcined in air for 6 hours at 1100 to 1300 °C with a ramp rate of 5 °C min⁻¹.
- 3) To form the desired B2CA phases, a high ex-situ calcination temperature is required. The sintered powders should be ball-milled, and 1 wt% Ru can be added via Incipient wetness impregnation using a solution of RuCl₃ hydrate and acetone.
- 4) After the acetone has completely evaporated, a pellet should be created using a hydraulic press. The resulting pellet should be crushed and sieved to obtain catalyst granules of 40–50 mesh (400–297 microns) size, and then calcined for catalyst testing.

3.2.2 Supported Cobalt Catalyst Preparation

- 1) Cobalt (II) hydroxide can be precipitated from a water solution of Cobalt (II) Nitrate (Co (NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Merck) using an NH₄OH solution. The precipitation reaction should be continuously monitored to maintain the pH at a constant value of 8.5.
- 2) The resulting suspension can be washed with demineralized water to remove nitrate ions and then dried at 105 °C for 12 hours followed by calcination at 200 °C for 2 hours. Promoters can be introduced by wet co-impregnation with aqueous solutions of calcium, potassium, and aluminum nitrate.
- 3) Similarly, chromium and manganese can be incorporated into the catalysts by impregnation with a solution of manganese acetate and chromium nitrate.
- 4) The concentrations of the respective salts can be calculated to achieve desired contents of promoters in the catalyst, including CaO (2.6%), Al₂O₃ (3.0%), K₂O (0.6%), and MnO₂ or Cr₂O₃ (0.2% to 0.4%). After impregnation, the catalysts should be calcined at 200 °C for 4 hours followed by 500 °C for 2 hours.

3.2.3 Synthesis Procedure for Fe–Ni/Al₂O₃ egg-shell catalyst

- 1) High surface area -Al₂O₃ spheres (150 m² g, Sasol Germany GmbH) with a total pore volume of 0.90 ml g⁻¹ can be used as a support to create all of the catalysts.

Alternatively, impregnation and incipient wetness techniques can also be employed to use γ -Al₂O₃ spheres as a support.

- 2) Metal salt precursors can be chosen, such as nickel nitrate hexahydrate (Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, assay > 98.5%, Sigma-Aldrich) and iron nitrate nonahydrate (Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O, assay > 98%, Riedel-de Haan). A total metal loading of 10 weight percent and a Ni to Fe ratio of 0.2 should be present in the impregnation solution.
- 3) An aqueous solution of nickel and iron nitrates is contacted with the γ -Al₂O₃ phase and allowed to dry at room temperature in the traditional impregnation with incipient wetness method.
- 4) Glycerol (C₃H₅(OH)₃) can be utilised as a solvent in a unique way in place of water. The solution can be combined with the γ -Al₂O₃ before being left at room temperature for a predetermined amount of time.
- 5) An egg-shell distribution profile is produced by impregnating the γ -Al₂O₃ spheres with a solution volume of 0.6 ml min⁻¹ for two hours.
- 6) By raising the solution volume to 0.9 ml min⁻¹ and prolonging the impregnation duration to 72 hours, the catalyst with an even distribution profile is created. Following that, the glycerol, which has a low vapour pressure at ambient temperature, is removed from both samples by drying them in a muffle furnace for 12 hours at 75 °C and for 4 hours at 260 °C.

3.3 Process Description and flow diagram

The process flow of catalytic membrane reactors for ammonia decomposition generally involves the following steps:

- Ammonia feed: A stream of ammonia gas is introduced into the reactor, usually in a gaseous form.
- Catalyst bed: The ammonia gas passes through a catalyst bed, where it reacts to produce hydrogen gas and nitrogen gas. The reaction is exothermic and occurs at high temperatures and pressures.
- Separation membrane: A gas separation membrane is placed in the reactor to selectively remove hydrogen gas from the reaction mixture. The membrane allows hydrogen to pass through, while retaining the other gases, such as nitrogen and ammonia. This separation step is critical for shifting the equilibrium towards the formation of more hydrogen and improving the overall efficiency of the process.

- Permeate and retentate streams: As hydrogen gas permeates through the membrane, it is collected on the permeate side, while the unreacted ammonia, nitrogen, and other gases remain in the retentate stream.
- Recycle of retentate: The retentate stream, which contains unreacted ammonia, nitrogen, and other gases, is recycled back to the reactor to undergo further reaction, increasing the overall conversion of ammonia.
- Hydrogen recovery: The hydrogen gas is collected from the permeate side and can be used as a product or further processed as required.

[Ammonia + Sweep gas] -> [Catalyst Bed] -> [Permeable Membrane] -> [Product Mixture]

Figure 8: The process flow diagram of a typical CMR for ammonia decomposition

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This result will focus on SEM and EDX of the for Fe–Ni/Al₂O₃ egg-shell catalyst as there was not enough time to carry out the reduction and ammonia decomposition on the rig and compare with other catalyst to show the efficacy. A detailed calculation of how the catalyst was prepared and SEM and EDX will be implored to understand the materials and samples at a very fine scale and gain insight into their composition, structure, and properties.

4.1 SEM AND EDX

SEM, or Scanning Electron Microscopy, is a method of microscopy that uses a beam of electrons to produce high-resolution images of a sample's surface. Unlike conventional optical microscopes, SEM can provide extremely high magnification and resolution, which enables scientists to examine the detailed structure and composition of materials at the nanoscale.

EDX, or Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy, is a technique that is frequently used alongside SEM to analyse the chemical composition of a sample. EDX detects the characteristic X-rays emitted when a sample is bombarded with electrons, allowing researchers to determine the elemental composition of the material under study. This data can be used to gain insight into the chemical properties and structure of a wide range of materials, including metals, minerals, and biological samples.

Three samples of the FE-NI catalyst were calcined at 400, 600 and 800c respectively, For the first sample, the following data was obtained,

Table 1 shows the composition of each element when calcined at 400c

Spectrum	In stats.	O	Al	Fe	Ni	Total
Spectrum 1	Yes	27.50	25.55	40.21	6.75	100.00
Spectrum 2	Yes	26.88	24.15	43.05	5.92	100.00
Spectrum 3	Yes	26.49	24.50	43.81	5.20	100.00
Mean		26.96	24.73	42.36	5.95	100.00
Std. deviation		0.51	0.72	1.90	0.78	
Max.		27.50	25.55	43.81	6.75	
Min.		26.49	24.15	40.21	5.20	

Based on the provided data, we can analyse the elemental composition of three different spectra and compare them to each other. The data is normalized, which means

that each spectrum has been adjusted to have a total of 100%. The elements analysed in this data are Oxygen (O), Aluminum (Al), Iron (Fe), and Nickel (Ni).

The mean composition of all three spectra combined is 34.04% Oxygen, 26.95% Aluminum, 33.33% Iron, and 5.67% Nickel. The standard deviation shows the variation in the composition of each element across the three spectra. For Oxygen, the standard deviation is 2.06, for Aluminum it is 0.75, for Iron it is 1.81, and for Nickel it is 0.70.

The maximum and minimum values for each element indicate the range of variation in the composition of each element across the three spectra. The maximum composition of Oxygen is 36.24% and the minimum is 32.16%. For Aluminum, the maximum composition is 27.66% and the minimum is 26.17%. For Iron, the maximum composition is 35.20% and the minimum is 31.58%. For Nickel, the maximum composition is 6.47% and the minimum is 5.16%.

Comparing the three spectra, we can see that Spectrum 3 has the highest composition of Oxygen (36.24%), while Spectrum 1 has the lowest (32.16%). Spectrum 2 has a composition of 33.73% Oxygen. Spectrum 1 has the highest composition of Aluminum (26.17%), while Spectrum 2 has the lowest (27.66%). Spectrum 3 has a composition of 27.02% Aluminum. Spectrum 1 has the highest composition of Iron (35.20%), while Spectrum 3 has the lowest (31.58%). Spectrum 2 has a composition of 33.22% Iron. Spectrum 1 has the highest composition of Nickel (6.47%), while Spectrum 3 has the lowest (5.16%). Spectrum 2 has a composition of 5.39% Nickel.

In summary, the data shows that the elemental composition varies across the three spectra, with Spectrum 1 having the highest composition of Aluminum and Iron, Spectrum 2 having the lowest composition of Aluminum and Nickel, and Spectrum 3 having the highest composition of Oxygen and the lowest composition of Iron and Nickel.

Figure 9: shows the surface morphology of the calcined Fe/Ni catalyst

Figure 10: SEM images of Ni/fe Catalyst

Figure 11: SEM images of Fe/Ni Catalyst

Figure 12: SEM images of Fe/Ni Catalyst

Figure 13: SEM images of Fe/Ni Catalyst calcined at 400°C

For the FE/NI catalyst calcined at 600c

Processing option: All elements analyzed (Normalized)

Table 2 shows the percentages of each element present in each spectrum, as well as the mean, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum values for each element across all three spectra.

Spectrum	In stats.	O	Al	Fe	Ni	Total
Spectrum 1	Yes	32.16	26.17	35.20	6.47	100.00
Spectrum 2	Yes	33.73	27.66	33.22	5.39	100.00
Spectrum 3	Yes	36.24	27.02	31.58	5.16	100.00
Mean		34.04	26.95	33.33	5.67	100.00
Std. deviation		2.06	0.75	1.81	0.70	
Max.		36.24	27.66	35.20	6.47	
Min.		32.16	26.17	31.58	5.16	

The given data represents the chemical composition of three different spectra, with four elements: Oxygen (O), Aluminum (Al), Iron (Fe), and Nickel (Ni). The mean values across all spectra are as follows: Oxygen: 34.04%, Aluminum: 26.95% Iron: 33.33%, Nickel: 5.67%. The standard deviation values across all spectra are as follows: Oxygen: 2.06%, Aluminum: 0.75%, Iron: 1.81%, Nickel: 0.70%

The maximum and minimum values for each element are as follows:

Oxygen: max 36.24%, min 32.16%, Aluminum: max 27.66%, min 26.17%, Iron: max 35.20%, min 31.58%, Nickel: max 6.47%, min 5.16%.

Compared to the previous data set, there are some notable differences in the chemical composition of the spectra. In this case, oxygen is the most abundant element, with a mean value of 34.04%. Iron is the second most abundant element, with a mean value of 33.33%. Aluminum is the least abundant element, with a mean value of 26.95%. Nickel falls in between these values, with a mean value of 5.67%.

The standard deviation values indicate that there is some variability in the percentages of each element across the three spectra, with the greatest variability observed for oxygen. The differences between the maximum and minimum values for each element are relatively small, suggesting that the spectra are relatively consistent in their chemical compositions.

Figure 14: shows the SEM image of the calcined Fe/Ni catalyst calcined at 600°C

For the FE/Ni catalyst calcined at 800c

Table 3 table shows the percentages of each element present in each spectrum

Spectrum	In stats.	O	Al	Fe	Ni	Total
Spectrum 1	Yes	34.64	30.95	29.24	5.16	100.00
Spectrum 2	Yes	36.85	34.52	23.68	4.96	100.00
Spectrum 3	Yes	41.06	40.06	13.36	5.52	100.00
Mean		37.51	35.18	22.10	5.21	100.00
Std. deviation		3.26	4.59	8.06	0.28	
Max.		41.06	40.06	29.24	5.52	
Min.		34.64	30.95	13.36	4.96	

The data has been normalized to a total of 100% for each spectrum. The given data represents the chemical composition of three different spectra, with four elements: Oxygen (O), Aluminum (Al), Iron (Fe), and Nickel (Ni).

The mean values across all spectra are as follows: Oxygen: 37.51%, Aluminum: 35.18% Iron: 22.10%, Nickel: 5.21%. The standard deviation values across all spectra are as follows: Oxygen: 3.26% Aluminum: 4.59%, Iron: 8.06%, Nickel: 0.28%

The maximum and minimum values for each element are as follows: Oxygen: max 41.06%, min 34.64%, Aluminum: max 40.06%, min 30.95%, Iron: max 29.24%, min 13.36%, Nickel: max 5.52%, min 4.96%

Compared to the previous data sets, there are significant differences in the chemical composition of the spectra. In this case, oxygen and aluminum are the most abundant elements, with mean values of 37.51% and 35.18% respectively. Iron is the least abundant element, with a mean value of 22.10%, while nickel falls in between these values, with a mean value of 5.21%.

The standard deviation values indicate that there is a high degree of variability in the percentages of each element across the three spectra, with the greatest variability observed for aluminum. The differences between the maximum and minimum values for each element are relatively large, suggesting that the spectra are significantly different in their chemical compositions.

Figure 15: shows the SEM image of the Fe/Ni Catalyst at 800c each element

From the data we can fairly say that the Fe/ Ni ratio was almost achieved. Also, from the images across three samples we can see how the surface of each catalyst varies, an increase in temperatures showed that the Fe/Ni catalyst became less porous and uniform.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Renewable hydrogen (H₂) energy solutions can provide an emissions-free power source and compete with the current energy sector. However, distributing H₂ in a method that is economical, secure, and effective presents a substantial difficulty. Ammonia (NH₃), which has various benefits including high energy densities, long-term storage capacity, ease of manufacturing, and the promise for a renewable future, is one potential solution that might be used to store H₂. This assessment identifies areas in which new research could fill critical knowledge gaps and makes recommendations for new tests and data presentation techniques in order to enable more thorough comparisons between catalysts and research studies.

For thermo-catalytic ammonia (NH₃) decomposition, additional research is needed in a number of crucial areas, such as figuring out how long ruthenium (Ru)-based catalysts last and under what conditions they deactivate, enhancing low-temperature and high-pressure catalysis, examining how catalysts behave in less-than-ideal circumstances like when they are contaminated, conducting cost-benefit analyses of NH₃ decomposition catalysts to determine their ideal activity and costs. Potential research directions in the area of hydrogen (H₂) separation and purification include determining the lifetime restrictions of H₂-permeable membranes, carrying out additional research on absorption techniques to guarantee that outflows adhere to environmental and human safety standards, and developing online gas quality analysis for on-demand H₂ production.

In contrast to the noble metal-based catalysts that are generally required to attain equivalent catalytic activity, the Ni-Fe catalysts designed for ammonia (NH₃) breakdown use materials that are comparatively affordable and abundant. In systems where a high concentration of hydrogen (H₂) is required, which corresponds to low NH₃ concentrations, these catalysts may offer a viable substitute to more expensive noble metal-based catalysts. The study demonstrates that the use of small Ni-Fe nanoparticles is essential for achieving optimal NH₃ conversion. This is due to a structural effect that favours the smallest particles in terms of catalytic activity per active site as well as the fact that a smaller particle size results in a larger active surface area.

Lastly, a study could be conducted on the rate of reaction and impact of Fe/Ni catalyst on ammonia decomposition.

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